

Scientific Article

Hydrogen reduction kinetics of a high-carbonate manganese ore in raw and calcined forms under isothermal conditions

Authors:

- **Alok Sarkar** and **Jafar Safarian**, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
- **Kai Tang** - SINTEF Industry, Trondheim, Norway

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.152919>

Co-funded by
the European Union